

AN APPROACH FOR DEALING WITH HIGH LOCAL STRESSES IN FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSES

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SUMMARY

A method for assessing the criticality of highly localised interlaminar stress concentrations in finite element analyses of composite structures is proposed, based on comparing the stresses with those due to a crack on the point of propagating. Examples of validation show the approach to give conservative results.

Keywords: Stress concentration, Fracture mechanics, Delamination, Failure initiation

INTRODUCTION

Highly localised stress concentrations, higher than the strength of the material, may occur when a linear elastic finite element analysis of a composite structure is performed. Such stresses may be caused by real discontinuities or by a problem in the model. The objective of this work is to develop validated criteria to determine when these high stresses will not lead to failure and can therefore be ignored. The method presented in this paper is named the “High Stress Concentration” or HSC method. It aims to help stress engineers to make a rational judgment on this issue with confidence. Its principle is simple. It consists in comparing, in the close neighbourhood of the stress concentration, the distribution of the obtained finite element stress levels with the distribution induced by the presence of an abstract crack on the point of propagating. If the stress levels encountered in the finite element analysis are less than what could be induced by this abstracted crack, they should be without consequences on the composite structure. After recalling some elements from the linear elastic fracture mechanics, the HSC method is presented. Two validation cases based on finite element analysis are presented: a unidirectional specimen with central cut plies; a curved beam specimen with cut plies. These cases show that the HSC method gives conservative results.

BACKGROUND THEORY

This section recalls some elements from the linear elastic fracture mechanics on which the HSC method is based. The definition of a loading mode problem is first presented within the framework of a finite element analysis, assuming no defects. Then, the concept of critical stress field ahead of an abstracted crack is outlined; the critical stress distribution is essentially dependent on the material fracture toughness. Finally an equivalent stress measure for mixed-mode unstable crack propagation will be

introduced; defining an equivalent stress field is necessary in order to directly compare the critical stress distribution, which represents the material toughness in mixed mode conditions, with the finite element stress field obtained in the HSC regions.

Definition of the loading mode concept

Providing both $\sigma > 0$ and $\tau \neq 0$ gives a local mixed-mode loading condition. According to the fracture mechanics theory [1, 2], there are three independent ways for a crack to propagate: the opening mode (mode I), the sliding mode (mode II) and the tearing mode (mode III). Figure 1 shows the crack surface displacements that generate the two first modes, the latter being usually ignored. They are defined provided that a crack is already present in the structure.

The principle of the HSC method is based upon a virtual interlaminar crack in a finite element mesh that does not include any damage. Under this condition, the only way of defining the loading modes is to refer to the stress tensor components using the primary stress components. As a consequence, the pure mode I loading will be defined when the normal through-thickness stress σ is positive. The pure mode II loading is defined locally when the interlaminar shear stress τ is non-zero. A stress tensor providing both $\sigma > 0$ and $\tau \neq 0$ gives a local mixed-mode loading condition.

Fig. 1: (a) Crack included into a layer. (b) Mode I surface displacements. (c) Mode II surface displacements.

Stress field ahead of a crack tip

According to the linear fracture mechanics theory and based upon the local basis drawn in figure 1, the singular stress field ahead of an interlaminar crack tip is given by the relation [2-4]:

$$\sigma = \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau = \frac{K_{II}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \quad (1)$$

In these equations, r is the distance from the interlaminar crack tip, K_I and K_{II} are respectively the mode I and mode II stress intensity factors defining the crack-tip singularity, and σ and τ are the normal stress and shear stress components. Equations (1) are theoretically valid in the close vicinity of the crack tip such that the $1/\sqrt{r}$ term predominates.

When the critical configuration is reached i.e. when the crack is just on the point of propagating, the stress intensity factors are equal to their critical values K_{Ic} and K_{IIc} that are material properties. As a consequence, equations (1) become:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{K_{Ic}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_c = \frac{K_{IIc}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \quad (2)$$

where respectively σ_c and τ_c are the critical normal and shear stresses. Both equations will be used for defining the critical curves in the HSC method.

Relationship between the energy release rate and the stress intensity factor

According to the crack closure analysis initially provided by Irwin [5], the energy release rate can be given as a function of the stress intensity factor using the following relations for mode I and mode II [2-4]:

$$G_I = \alpha_I K_I^2 \quad \text{and} \quad G_{II} = \alpha_{II} K_{II}^2 \quad (3)$$

The coefficients α_I and α_{II} are defined according to the mode, the configuration and the material [4]:

$$\alpha_I = \sqrt{\frac{a_{11}a_{33}}{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{a_{33}}{a_{11}} + \frac{2a_{13} + a_{55}}{2a_{11}}} \right)^{1/2} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_{II} = \frac{a_{11}}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{a_{33}}{a_{11}} + \frac{2a_{13} + a_{55}}{2a_{11}}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Since the critical fracture toughnesses G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are generally well-known, these values will help to determine the critical curves defined by equations (2).

Definition of the equivalent stress

A pure mode I or mode II condition that enables a crack to propagate occurs in particularly loading conditions at the boundary of the structure. Generally, a crack is subject to mixed-mode loading conditions. It is therefore necessary to account for this mode-mixity in predicting the delamination propagation.

Several empirical laws allow accounting for this combination [6]. One of them is the simple and widely-used power-law energetic mixed-mode fracture criterion defined by the relation [6, 7]:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} \right)^n + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} \right)^n \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

Reorganising the different terms and introducing equations (3) into in this equation (5), it follows:

$$K_I^{2n} + g^n K_{II}^{2n} \geq K_{Ic}^{2n} \quad \text{with} \quad g = \frac{G_{Ic}}{G_{IIc}} \frac{\alpha_{II}}{\alpha_I} \quad (6)$$

Substituting equations (1) and (2) into the stress intensity factors from equation (6), one obtains:

$$\sigma_{\text{eq}} = (\sigma^{2n} + g^n \tau^{2n})^{\frac{1}{2n}} \geq \sigma_c \quad (7)$$

The above defined quantity σ_{eq} is the “mode I equivalent stress”. This equation (7) means that failure occurs once this mode I equivalent stress is equal or greater than the pure mode I critical stress defined in equations (2). As a consequence, to analyse a mixed-mode loading case, it is sufficient to compare this equivalent stress curve with the mode I critical stress curve only. This comparison is one of the original points from the principle of the HSC method. The normal stress component is implicitly a positive value as a negative one would lead to a pure state of compression that does not contribute to failure by delamination [8]. It may also be mentioned that, similarly to equation (7), it would have been possible to introduce the mode II equivalent stress by writing $\tau_{\text{eq}} = (g^{-n} \sigma^{2n} + \tau^{2n})^{1/2n} \geq \tau_c$.

PRINCIPLE OF THE HSC METHOD

According to all the elements introduced previously, the assumptions allowing the definition of the HSC method are as follows:

- a) The material is orthotropic i.e. composed of one material only or is considered as being a block of several plies with arbitrary orientations but entirely homogenised.
- b) The abstracted crack is within the single material.
- c) The material is assumed to have a linear elastic behaviour so that linear elastic fracture mechanics applies.
- d) The fracture criterion accounting for the mode-mixity is the linear energetic one given in equation (5) with $n = 1$. It is perhaps the most often referred to in the literature [6]. Obviously the more general case with the general form of the power-law criterion could easily be used but, in the following, the presentation is restricted to a unitary value of n .

Method for pure mode I or mode II loading

For the case of a pure loading mode analysis, the HSC method is based upon a comparison between the finite element stress distribution in the neighbourhood of the high stress concentration and a critical curve when the finite element stress values, i.e. the through thickness components $\sigma_{\text{F.E.}}$ or the shear stress components $\tau_{\text{F.E.}}$, are respectively over the strength of the material, σ_{max} or τ_{max} .

For a pure mode I loading problem, the method aims to compare the through thickness tensile stress distribution ahead of the stress concentration with the mode I critical stress curve $\sigma_c(r)$ defined in equations (2). In the vicinity of the high stress concentration, failure occurs if:

$$\text{Max}\{\sigma_{\text{F.E.}}, 0\} \geq \sigma_c \quad \text{when} \quad \sigma_{\text{F.E.}} \geq \sigma_{\text{max}} \quad (8)$$

In the case of a pure mode II loading problem, the method is based on comparing the distribution of the absolute value of the interlaminar shear stresses in the vicinity of the stress concentration with the mode II critical stress curve $\tau_c(r)$ defined in equations (2). In the vicinity of the high stress concentration, failure occurs if:

$$|\tau_{F.E.}| \geq \tau_c \quad \text{when} \quad |\tau_{F.E.}| \geq \tau_{max} \quad (9)$$

In equations (8) and (9), the critical curves given by $\sigma_c(r)$ and $\tau_c(r)$ are defined according to equations (2). The critical stress intensity factor values K_{Ic} and K_{IIc} are defined from equations (3) and the corresponding critical energy release rates G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are known from experimental measurements [2]. Any other case that does not meet the criterion given in equations (8) or (9) leads to a finite element stress concentration that may not be safely ignored. In this condition, this means that a crack should initiate and propagate unstably along the chosen local x-axis from the location where the high stress concentration has been observed.

Fig. 2: Principle of the HSC method for a pure mode I or mode II loading problem.

Method for a mixed-mode loading problem

The cases of a pure mode I or mode II loading problem are encountered for simple tests only. A general situation may involve both modes and both stress components $\sigma_{F.E.}$ and $\tau_{F.E.}$ can be picked-up ahead of a stress concentration [9].

To account for the interaction between both stress components $\sigma_{F.E.}$ and $\tau_{F.E.}$, the equivalent stress introduced in equation (7) is used. This mode I equivalent finite element stress may be written as:

$$\sigma_{eq} = \sqrt{\text{Max}^2 \{ \sigma_{F.E.}, 0 \} + g \tau_{F.E.}^2} \quad \text{with} \quad g = \frac{G_{Ic} \alpha_{II}}{G_{IIc} \alpha_I} \quad (10)$$

It predicts interlaminar failure once the contribution of the finite element normal and shear stress components generate a mode I equivalent stress that is higher than or equal to the mode I critical stress of a crack on the point of propagating within the material considered.

EXAMPLES OF APPLICATION VALIDATING THE HSC METHOD

Mode II loading: Unidirectional specimen with central cut plies

To illustrate and validate the applicability of the method in pure Mode II loading, we consider a unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy test specimen with cut central plies across its full width in pure tension, see figure 3. This particular case has been studied extensively over the past years and its behaviour is well known, see [9-11]. The discontinuous plies cause an interlaminar shear stress concentration. Very high values above the strength of the material are generated even at low loads, and these could safely be ignored. However these stresses do lead to delamination once a critical load is reached. The normal stresses near the cut are compressive except at the extremity of the cut plies. Therefore this test can be considered to be a mode II case. The mechanical properties of the E-glass fibre / 913 resin epoxy are given in [12, 13].

Fig. 3: Finite element geometric model of the unidirectional test specimen with central cut plies (quarter-geometry).

To simulate by the finite element method this tested specimen, a two dimensional analysis of a slice through the thickness was carried out in plane stress. The mesh was built using Abaqus/CAE using fully integrated quadratic elements of type CPS8. Due to the presence of planes of symmetry, only a quarter-model was used as schematically shown in figure 3.. Using a 744 MPa applied tension on the entire cross section which is close to the 772.8 MPa experimentally measured failure propagation stress on the test specimen, the finite element results give a shear stress curve close to the ply discontinuity, see figure 4. This curve has been obtained picking-up the finite element stress values along the interface between the continuous and cut plies. The peak of stress is much higher than the interlaminar shear strength τ_{\max} estimated at 75 MPa [13].

Fig. 4: Finite element curve for a 744 MPa applied gross section stress versus the critical shear stress curve.

Applying the HSC method using $G_{IIC} = 1.08 \text{ N/mm}$, the result is conservative for the 744 MPa applied gross section tensile stress on the test specimen, see figure 4. The finite element curve is under the critical one in the close neighbourhood of the stress concentration where the stresses are higher than the shear strength of the material. Under these conditions, this level of stress may be ignored according to the principle of the HSC method. This is consistent with the experimental results which showed that the delamination initiated at 726 MPa, but did not propagate until a 765 MPa average gross stress value, see [10].

Mixed-mode loading: Unidirectional curved beam specimen with cut plies

The applicability of the method for a pure mixed-mode problem is illustrated by considering a glass fibre / epoxy resin curved beam in four-point bending, see figure 5. This kind of geometry with and without cut plies across the width has been studied extensively by Wisnom and co-workers, see [11-15] for more details. This test produces theoretically a pure bending moment over the inner span. The geometry and its dimensions are given in figure 5. The material properties are given in [12, 13]. The lay-up is $(0_6/\bar{0}_4/0_{22})$ from the lowermost to the uppermost ply with a bar indicating the selected plies cut.

Fig. 5: Curved beam specimen dimensions (mm)

The linear elastic finite element simulation was performed using a plane stress model of the half geometry, see figure 6. The mesh was built using Abaqus/CAE using fully integrated quadratic elements of type CPS8. A 60 N/mm load per unit width on the upper roller has been applied. This value is equivalent to a 1800 Nmm/mm bending moment per unit width, close to the experimental 1802 Nmm/mm bending moment at failure [11, 13]. To account for the expected high stress concentration, a refined mesh was used in the vicinity of the cut plies: 4 elements per ply, of size 31.25 μm in the radial direction and 95.192 μm in the circumferential direction, see figure 6. On the portion far from the cut, a coarse mesh was used to reduce the number of degrees of freedom in the whole of the numerical system to be solved.

Fig. 6: Through thickness stress field S22 and interlaminar lines to plot the stress distributions starting from the high stress concentrations.

Applying the HSC method using $G_{lc} = 0.25$ N/mm and $G_{llc} = 1.08$ N/mm, the result is conservative for an applied load per unit width of 60 N/mm, see figure 7. The finite element curve is just under the critical one, indicating that the specimen is very close to failure. The very high stresses that would still be present at slightly lower loads may therefore be ignored.

Fig. 7: Equivalent stresses distributions versus the mode I critical curve.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a method allowing to assess the criticality of high localised stress concentrations in linear elastic finite element analyses has been defined. It is based upon the linear fracture mechanics theory for orthotropic materials. Applications on some extreme cases have given good conservative results and have validated the method. The next step is to present how to use the method on general 3D finite element analyses and to tackle the case of stress concentrations at multi-material interfaces

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